

TECHNICAL ANALYSIS ON THE CYBER ORGANIZATIONAL CRIMINOLOGY OF DICTATORIAL MILITARY CONDUCTS -- EXPERIENCE FROM HUMAN TRAFFICKING AND COERCIONS BY MILITARY CYBER AGGRESSIONS

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ABSTRACT

The reformulated paper after the proceeding of the NCWMC 2022 recovers some previous manuscripts intercepted by the PLA of PRC for covert military operations with intrusions in global investment and financial systems. The crimes are analytically conducted through cloud servers and I/O for intelligence gathering. The information contained in the manuscripts with THEIR informatics not only could have led to further economic-financial surrogation of the PLA in American economy with investments, but also threats American national security through ontological calculation frameworks with artificial intelligence and further calculative power assertions - apart from the threats of outer space peace and security. It can be the reason behind the black hole and white hole observational results with the signal-satellite-information approach to general relativity manuscripts. A preliminary conception for defense strategy is proposed with previous insights and post facto security breaches to USA Space Command directly and national security conductively.

KEYWORDS

Space Command, National Security, Human Trafficking, Military Intelligence, Black Hole Information

1. INTRODUCTION

With the prior alert on myself being human trafficked by the People's Liberation Army (PLA) of the PRC during my attempt to fulfill my cisgender homosexual marriage, I noticed that some companies based in Shenzhen, PRC have been conducting keyboard trafficking on personal devices – possibly on behalf of the dictatorial semantic networks and associated with the higher education system of the regime for artificial intelligence (AI) calculations in the topological ontologies of internet protocol distributions. [1] It was with this regard, I installed with consent on NASA's Eyes to monitor my keyboard, and Federal Common Policy on iPhone to have a possible general protection on my personal device from being used for covert psychological & psychosocial calculations. [2] A push notification on WeChat from Xinhua News long before it grabbed with Russia to "oppose the deployment of nuclear weapon in outer space" brought to my consciousness how ignorant the dictatorial regime is, and made me aware that they could have possibly been leading disastrous outer space programmes. [3] With the pathologies in coercion theory, "few military officers see killing and dying as just a form of communication" and the Maoist thought predominant in the Communist Party of China (CPC) one of them. [4] [5]

truth of my theory empirically or based on professor Daly's works so that we can have a point to start with, therefore, I recovered the non-empirical expression from the codes that recorded my writing process verbatim on *post facto* basis of my experiment results - I only had to send my ugly hand-drawing to her via email after my manuscripts became inaccessible by APP with the interceptions. The contents of the manuscripts are based on the satellite-information-cyber-computer signal analysis with computer information reconstruction approach to general relativity (GR). [11] It sought to advance the paradigm of global distribution to a solar-information distribution, and address the rightful uses of AI in the nuclear & astronomical sciences instead of the gross human rights transgression uses on dictatorial society & resources calculations that is implemented with the PRC's regime cyber conducts. [12]

The regime human traffickers (cyber Gestapo of the Chinese dictator institutionally named Ministry of State Security of the People's Republic of China) and human rights abusing military surveillance usually have to make use of DNS and intranet cloud environment for device tracking shown in *Figure 2*, with contrast to dynamic DNS perceptions of open internet in space-based (and ground-based) telescopes. [12] Albeit ground-based telescopes have usually been used for global distribution purposes, the research adopted the earth's electromagnetism in combination with Euclidean & Archimedean geometries to boost research efficacy and overcome the limitations of experiment environment. My perception and insight in the dynamic DNS environment begot from my 2019 field trip in USA with a GR thinking that always accompanied my international trips for psychological time dilation in the earth's protocols on time & timezones in a solar-centric setting, and in the interactions with computer systems.

Figure 2. Diagram on the research & experiment environment

Apart from my purpose in counteracting the human trafficking schemes of the illicit & human rights abusing regime, the perception and insights on the electronic amplification on the new MacBook Pro Baryonic arms chip for computer-satellite astrophysical science information paradigm was conceptually drawn on my notebook in 2019 shown in *figure 3* after I had to return to PRC for the FBI and / or NSA's following me while I tried to file for asylum reporting the gross human rights abuses with secondary source organizational & technical evidence in *appendix Aof* the conference paper. [5] [13] The three Simplified Chinese wordings mean "information streaming time differentiation", "feedback time differentiation", and "verification time differentiation", and it is put alongside the notes on the quantum readings of astrophysical

sciences. These pilot researches upon the dictatorial shifts of PRC for countering their human trafficking in reporting the gross human rights transgressions in the cyber space both on my human rights and many more other populations unaware of the situations, paved the basis for my research methods developed during the *Astronomy: Exploring Time and Space* Coursera course with access to the open science practice of data and *Harvard-Smithsonian MicroObservatory*. These are complemented with satellite kernels and caches in the computational GR conceptualization for black hole information. With the insights on NASA Deep Space Network's limitation of four bands, the number theory construct on the numerals was set to $0 \approx \frac{1}{i^{4n}}$ and every whole number $\approx i^{4n} + n$. [14] [15]

Figure 3. Previous conceptual drawing on the satellite signal paradigm approach to GR in Computer Science and Quantum Information

2. CURRENT STATE OF BLACK HOLE KNOWLEDGE

The theoretical underpinnings of black hole (BH) were established on detection methods of photons. Professor Ruth A. Daly's new methods of BH study is focused on spin and accretion disk. The new method is composed of three parts, i.e., radioactive detection of BH outflows, chemical trace detection of accretion disk fusion, and gravitational lensing of professor Priyamvada Natarajan in complement to Professor Daly's method. The methodology of the empirical relations can be explained by available instrumentation, summarized as high energy space telescope survey with ergosphere, physical observational limit of light defined by event horizon of interferometry survey, and limitations of space travel defined by manmade energy against the objects in question defined as BHs.

The theorization of BH components can be largely advanced by two directions, i.e., fusion waste of condense matters and anti-graviton. Professor Daly's talks archived on Penn State website implied that the chemical process of BHs can be reversed. But it doesn't mean the chemistry involved is entirely known by chemistries applied on earth or in space stations. It means that in

order to confirm or develop further empirical knowledge on BHs, space exploration is still important. The theoretical development of BH study is in dark matter and anti-matter experiments represented by LHC and European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN). The knowledge management system is with International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP)'s High Energy, Cosmology and Astroparticle Physics (HECAP). Bolometric disk luminosity L_{bol} is the indicator for lab experiment.

In current observational methods the four types of BH cataloguing are unified by Einstein's special relativity (SR) with gravitational lensing. The field of developmental study is photoelectric effect for Reissner-Nordström and Kerr-Newman BHs, and high energy effect for Kerr and Kerr-Newman BHs. The lab science for BH study and further instrumentation is the fusion community represented by International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), International Thermonuclear Experimental Reactor (ITER) and astronomical communities of national space agencies. The theorization of BH elements mainly focuses on fusion and organized by ITER in plasma physics, and the CERN in particle physics. Current academic trends are on exoplanet and transit. This is a sustainable approach. If there is observational apparatus in place and deployed, the explorer with nuclear power source in interstellar location could be considered an option to observed the event horizon. [11]

2.1. Methodological Analysis: Current Establishment of BH Chemistry on Earth

The observed momentum of the observed BH's mass loss is determined by the Eddington Limit $M = \frac{p}{c}$ with a presumption of spherically symmetric emission. The mass of the BH is then inferred by the companion star or accretion luminosity of the BH $L_{accretion} = \epsilon \dot{M} c^2$, whereas \dot{M} denotes the gas inflow rate (the accretion rate) with unit G/sec denoting the radioactive efficiency, depending on the sources of timekeeping. Within the ionosphere's chemistry, the mass of a BH is described as comparative to the solar setting, therefore, the inference to the exchanged mass between a BH and its companion star or galaxy denoted as M' . In assumption that a BH is solid cored, the maximum rate at which a BH can accrete gas is to set accretion luminosity equal to the Eddington limit $L_{Edd} = L_{Accretion}$. This gives $M_{\odot} = \frac{\epsilon \dot{M} c \kappa}{4\pi G}$ in heliocentric reference system in relation to space telescopes on earth regime $L'_{Edd} = \frac{4\pi c G M}{\kappa}$, whereas the speed of light in GR is expressed as $c \approx 0.12 \frac{Au}{min}$. In SI base unit $R = 6.3781 \times 10^6 km$ for space telescopes in geocentric reference system $\alpha \approx 6,378.1370 km$, $\beta \approx 6,356.7523 km$.

In astronomical sciences the mass of a BH can only be estimated by high energy surveys from space telescopes. It rests on the Einstein equation $E = M c^2$ on the accretion luminosity of the BH $\rho = \frac{E}{c}$ in a dimensionless setting of the observed BH phenomenon. The observed momentum of the BH's change in mass M' is determined by the Eddington Limit $L_{Edd} = \frac{4\pi c G M'}{\kappa}$ in Thomson scattering with presumption of spherically symmetric emission in the momentum flux $\frac{L}{4\pi c r^2}$, whereas r denotes either source's radius. The mass of the BH is then inferred by the companion star or galaxy with accretion luminosity of the BH $L_{Accretion} = \epsilon \dot{M}_{wh}$ with $r_c = 6.3781 \times 10^3 km$. This puts the Einstein's equation intact. For fusion survey space telescopes in geocentric reference system the cryogenic CCD's threshold $\lambda = 120K$ (albeit in the quantum information system in the observation experiments, the thermal capacity of cryogenic CCD far proceeded this expectation). [10] Figure 4 was the Schwarzschild observation conceptualization before the experiments.

2.2. The Binary Construct of Black Hole Information

A conjecture in number theory with regard to ascension, descension, and operational decisions was conceived that whenever the square root of n is irrational, the root of n by itself is irrational. With an initial test on the conjecture with $n = e^m$ as m moves in the directions of either positive

Figure 4. Concept drawing on the Schwarzschild BH structure

or negative infinity, the number either becomes too large for a calculator to handle or goes to 1. A BH has mass was predicted by SR, and observed by space telescope surveys. The singularity of a BH is determined by the observed photons from astro-particle light chemistry interactions. A BH event horizon is determined by the theoretical object's existence and induction from observed events. The spacetime curvature on a BH event horizon (or say the coordinate system on spacetime curved by a BH) can be described by Euler's polyhedron formula with one vertex as the BH singularity:

$$F + V - 2 = E \quad (1)$$

Every face F is a spacetime fabric, every vertical V is a potential timeline on the exertion of force, -2 can be seen as the binary state of both in and out (I/O) of astro-particles on the

singularity, and every edge E is the potential energy of every astro-particle released from the singularity. In every F , every astro-particle's basic state E on the BH vertex of every V is described by de Moivre's formula:

$$E = (\cos\theta + i\sin\theta)^n = \cos n\theta + i\sin n\theta \quad (2)$$

In a quantitative sense in computational astronomy or cosmology, the sum of the angular momentum can be simplified with Euler's formula as $E = e^{in\theta}$.

In introducing astro-particles in the coordinate system the original state of the matter shall be described by force (distribution), electric charge, radioactivity, temperature, etc. First when I go to force in the space time, the angular momentum of the astro-particles curves the spacetime as weak force with Newton's third law. [16] Since in every and all possible spacetime F , an astro-particle can only have one physical state of force, curve, distance, velocity - let it be the angular momentum of an astro-particle on singularity, the sum of astro-particles' distribution on all possible faces can be described by de Moivre's formula:

$$(\cos\theta + i\sin\theta)^F = \cos F\theta + i\sin F\theta \quad (3)$$

The sum of the angular momentum can be simplified with Euler's formula as $e^{iF\theta} = E$. Thus, the accretion disk of a BH can be described as: ... (The manuscript was inserted with too much encryption from there on to be recognized, apart from the repetition, but deviations from the recovered parts can still be built upon. Another dimensional assertion recovered from the codes is $\sum F + \sum V - 2 = \sum E$, and this part consists of $M_{BH} \cap M_{VIC}$.) [10]

Since every face the distribution of the astro-particle has an angular momentum to the singularity vertex, $\cos\theta$ describes the distance between the astro-particle and singularity. Since there is only one true state of the astro-particle in question, the dimensional distribution of the astro-particle can be written as $\cos F\theta$. This describes the event horizon of the astro-particles moving out from the singularity. $\sin\theta$ is written for linear observation on the event. The dimensional aspect of the observed event is thus $\sin F\theta$. *Figure 5* is a representation on the graphic and geometric conceptualization on the space and time around a black hole singularity: [15]

Figure 5. The conceptual drawing on the dimensions of space and time on BH singularity

3. KINETICS AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Since I have been in the military information gathering and governmental apparatus human trafficking & enslaving regime's DNS-server environment inside the Great Firewall of PRC, the kinetics part has been both full of security risk concerns with real breaches in the algorithm & API driven scientific community environment, and possible biases from the intrusive signals' adverse impacts on my mental & psychological health. [2] With the prerequisite knowledge on the human trafficking regime conduct and rationale on its domain politics, I tried my best in differentiating the criminal activities from my research on the celestial bodies. *Figure 6* is a diagram on the primary research I took on for the criminal activities I observed in and during the MBA program in Communication University of China with its adverse impacts on the global open internet environment, apart from the economic surrogation of it for power political & realpolitik military purposes. [2] [5] [12] [17]

Figure 6. Flowchart of the Organizational Criminology

Apart from the organizational criminology of the dictatorial group with bureaucratic bases for population enslavement with appearances of governmental formalism, the research's primary focus was on finding the BH and WH on NGC 3034 with multispectral data analytics. [16] How to leverage earth is the starting point for all astronomical sciences. The fundamental instruments of observational astronomy cannot be fully utilized without the former, neither can black holes be more thoroughly studied and detected without modern leverage on the instruments. The geocentric protocols of time on earth set a limitation for observational astronomy. The first leverage needs to be utilized is the concept of time itself. Governmental bodies are designed by geocentric and Newtonian physics. Information systems are either earthbound satellite signals or cables underground and underseas. Such concentration of data flows determined regional protocols of time on a geocentric basis. However, such everyday concepts of time set a limit on reading farther astronomical bodies. Space telescope and interferometry instrumentations have leveraged earth and heliocentric space in the solar system. Yet in consideration of BHs how to trace them among all the light sources lies at the central purpose of this research – an expression on self-regulation in Gestalt psychodynamics.

The basic philosophical objectives on an astronomical BH are: 1. A BH has mass; 2. A BH exists independently of the event on observing; 3. Astronomical BHs are traceable with known properties. According to the works of David Bohm, by observation, time consciousness is implied of the observer. Such consciousness is the basis of differentiating light sources and sources that absorb light, in all spectrums. The legacy sample data contained in this experimental work are from space telescope instrumentations of Spitzer, Chandra X-ray, GALEX, and Hubble

on NGC 3034. The readings of the sample were aided by JS9-4L online, FITS headers, and SAOImageDS9 with histograms & zScale. [18] [19] [20] [21] [22] [23]

In a natural outer space environment spots of higher energy flow to lower energy. With space telescope instrumentations it means a solar or earth-bound time vector, implying the observers. The Chandra X-ray dataset composes of high, mid, and low energies, with layers inside each sample file in -32 pixel depth. Pixel values were primarily used to determine if each dissect contains information of matters. The Spitzer dataset were primarily used to determine time with its heliocentric orbit. It consists of mid and near infrared samples, which eliminates radial information of the source. The samples are in -64 pixel depth. GALEX and Hubble dataset are in -64 pixel depth and used to compare with Chandra X-ray's energy traces in order to supplement the Chandra dataset's pixel depth difference. The radial rotation in Chandra X-ray low energy, GALEX, and Hubble samples can be grouped for plasma traces of the observer bound substances, and they were all on geocentric orbit.

While the high and mid energy samples were used to form a visual representation of the source BH, the Spitzer dataset were used to see the thermo- electro effect on the BH where the fusion occurred and observed on vicinity. The quantum thermo-conductivity on imagery information suggests the energy source is charged with extremely low temperature. The electromagnet ring is visualized with the Spitzer sample dataset. This supplements the explanation for information lost on the central radial sphere in Chandra X-ray dataset due to thermal transmission in outer space. The results suggest further studies on the accretion disk and singularity by weak force calculation may lead to further understandings on cold fusion particles. The recombined multispectral kinematics on the DCE whole array on the direct histogram from multi-mission space telescopes is in *figure 7* after the positive results of the Kerr-Newman. [16] [2] [8]

My original proposition in the article was based on the concern in the politics around ITER with the military dictatorship's use of AI with illicit power political, realpolitik, and coercion models of organizational crimes that contribute to the gross human rights transgressions & abuses. It is with the ongoing aggressions on Ukraine, I reported in the addendum on detected PRC dictatorial group's manipulations on the identity card data from the backend for their illicit energy political crimes through financial data manipulation by centralized banking & monetary means linked to civil economy during my self-recovery from psychological harm with their outer space thermonuclear contamination by QUESS while I was still trying to recover from the harms & trauma from their human trafficking. [9] [6] After I decided to publish my result on *Academia Letters*, the platform algorithm started pushing paper relevant to my research with my name as author but not written by me. Those have been more detailed information on the mathematical, biological and nuclear aspects of my research. No direct evidence has been drawn yet from the PLA military spying & information extracting operations, but quite some of my manuscripts submitted to *Academia Letters* experienced deliberate espionage review, including direct threats on my public health & ecological manuscript, not long before the journal stopped publishing – on a temporary basis. Its correlations with *figure 6* could explain the poison pen letter that may or may not be mailed from New York with the export-import control regime centralized banking monetary control and covert military conducts in commercial banking financial domains. [13] The subjective aspects of psycho-quantum-information construct paved the basis for the theorem that completes both the white hole observation experiment and starting place for the gravitation theorem. [10] [6]

Figure 7. The multispectral histogram kinematic of the BH on NGC 3034 showing the thermonuclear explosive dynamics with electroweak waves

The inertial astro-particles' distance to the singularity θ is determined by the inertial movement of the particle. Every face the distribution of the astro-particle has an angular momentum to the singularity vertex, $\cos \theta$ describes the distance between the astro-particle and singularity at the $\tan \theta$ position of the observer (there is only one event that actually exists and observed by the observer). Since there is only one true state of the astro-particle in question, the dimensional distribution of the astro-particle can be written as $\cos F\theta$. This is the distance between the astro-particle and singularity. $\sin \theta$ is written for the observed distance between the astro-particle and singularity. The dimensional aspect of the observed distance is thus $\sin F\theta$. The distance between the astro-particle and singularity observed can thus be written in equation (3) \equiv inertial mass distance. It can be used separately or as in pair, with the latter for my choice in experiment for the long-foreseen thermonuclear environment in the theory.[8] When used as in pair, $\sum e^{iF\theta}$ describes the simultaneity of the multi-spectrality sources observed and the astro-physic-chemical aspect underlying the event. V describes the inertial state of the astro-particles. A server-side big data theorem was also contained in the manuscript intercepted by the PLA.

$$\sum F + \sum V - 2 = \sum E \quad (4)$$

For the right courses of action with server & cloud computing regarding kinematics, cosmology, information, GR, and the FITS protocols, an information-based paradigm for methodology in cosmology was meant to be proposed in The Science of Consciousness 2022 conference in the University of Arizona, but intruded by the Chinese dictatorial group with governmental apparatus – both for in-person and in remote settings. *Figure 8* is a diagram on the proposed concept sent to the conference organizer in the PPT. Four spheres of spaces have been differentiated in the proposed methodology:

Figure 8. Quantum Physics, Computer Science, and Satellite Application (Orbital Science) Correlates

A. Solar Space as Instrumentation Space:

- Increased factorials with light speed in information;
- Top domain spiders for orbital control & command loops – with United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs or military;
- Flexible adjustments with informatic patches;

B. Solar Metadata in GR

- Projections of astronomical / celestial planes instead of the current World Coordinate System(WCS) schemes;
- Change FITS files' current WCS to a more flexible float algorithm such as in GUI;

C. SR and Lorentz Transformation as Astrochemistry & Astrophysical Information

- Imaging (cryogenic) plates are the fundamental physical information on the cosmic scale;
- Limitations on spectroscopy will still be there including with incomplete material absorption and the need for signal strength entropies;
- Electromagnetism and nuclear forces can be reassembled in data, and gravitational data can be embedded with correlation to orbital floats (current WCS);

D. Computation Base

- Quantum floats are best suitable for gravitation, i.e., operations, and traditional binaries best suit for astrophysical & astrochemical purposes;
- Domain distributions of topological function data, which may make the perception of physics in astronomy more fragmented;
- Momenta data such as arrays have more reference in energy and less in spatial distribution in the Big Bang theory (BB), which can be put as computed modeling.

In the series of observation and experiment, the fifth cosmic force as the force between a BH and a WH is expressed as $\left(\frac{i-1}{i}\right)^n * \left(\frac{i+1}{i}\right)^n$ with "*" place-hold for electromagnetism or $\left(\frac{i-1}{i}\right)^n * \left(\frac{i+1}{i}\right)^{n-1}$ with reduced power. With global distribution properties $BB \in i\pi$, and $G_{\mu\nu}$ can be replaced by incoming black hole seeds. Therefore, with discrete math black hole shadows can be further studied, and with less discrete math white hole seeds and white holes can be further studied. [24] Therefore, the quantum dimension of time extensions was formulated as: [13]

$$i\hat{h} \frac{\delta}{\delta t} \psi(x, t) = \left[-\frac{\hat{h}^2}{2m} \frac{\delta}{\delta x^2} + V(x, t) \right] \psi(x, t) \quad (5)$$

Further empirical differentiation was put in the term of $2m$.

4. RESULTS

With a discrete description on my number theory, I have been trying to find the simplest way to summarize prime number for many years, which is associated with my perception on the exotic metal insulator in BH & WH seeds collision momentum shown in *figure 9*. [9] In my Coursera course with prof. Keith Devlin's axiom to the Goldbach Conjecture in *figure 10*, I built from there to my axiom of description on prime numbers that supplement the WH observation paper. [10]

Figure 9. The hot representation on the exotic metal insulator on Trifid Nebula in WH observation

Figure 10. The original proof of Prof. Devlin's

Take $n = p + q + 3, n > 5$ and is odd:

$$\begin{aligned} n - 1 &= p + q + 2 = 2P_2P_3 \dots P_m + 3 + q \\ &= 2(P_2P_3 \dots P_m + 1) + (q + 1) \text{ and gives both even numbers} \\ &= 4x + 2y, x \text{ and } y \text{ are odd} - \text{rewritten as functionable plots} \end{aligned}$$

$\frac{n-1}{2} = 2x + y$ gives the proof on the binary data root with the Goldbach Conjecture, and the collision momentum shown in figure 11 is written as $\frac{n}{q-1} - 1 = \frac{p+1}{q-1}$ with $q - 1 \propto n$ or $q - 1 \propto (p + 1)$.

Figure 11. The BH & WH seeds collision momentum on NGC 3034 ring singularity

5. CONCLUSIONS

Even though in a restrained situation, the observational & data experiments suggest the scientific-technological design is executable with current availability of technologies with the prerequisite evaluations in the conference paper. The shell designs in topology can follow the terrestrial-astronomical-celestial spheres with computer-satellite-data dissections in time and space with

instrumentation-scientist-operations feedback loops on an organizational scale. Gravitational degradation from the BH & WH could have contributed to the broken of SPITZER Space Telescope from the multispectral data analysis shown in *figure 12*. It is also with this regard, the sharpness and precision of the design constructs may lead to instrumentation destructive results. The precision and correctness in gravitation theory are not the desirable input for satellite & instrumentation, and a flexible adjustment zone is necessary within a bearable bias range. From the onset of the NASA Data Challenge history, multispectral surveys have been a recent operation, and coordinated actions in space-based instrumentation may have risks in electroweak force on the whole systems' short circuit. The projection from terrestrial to celestial spheres with energy paradigm have high costs in operation that may lead with regional conflicts with current global situations. It is also with the values of the astronomical sciences and data to the real economy and education sectors based on the autonomy principle on the inherent dignities and conscience of human beings, an open internet with Net Neutrality and unobstructed access to information is paramount both for the people of PRC and people of the world.

Figure 12. The gravitational degradation with neutron degeneration on NGC 3034 with thermonuclear binding of BH & WH and possibly lost information on the fifth cosmic force

As with my experience of being human trafficked with psychological attacks, even with my long deliberate erratic behaviour pre-designed for their perception and my own mental health in the human rights abusive cyber & communication surveillance environment caused by structural dictatorship and institutionally implemented coercion mechanisms, the "new media" technology-driven propaganda machine has gained more power for reversing the psychological and psychoanalytic processes developed before World War I and contributed to the public mental health during World War II. The commercialization of such manipulative designs & algorithms has been even less detectable by traditional psychologists & psychoanalysts for the occultation process. [25] Modern mass surveillance and military intelligence's calculative power intrusion mechanism shown in *figure 13* for psychological coercion and threats have unprecedentedly burdened the public & mental health systems – apart from the medical systems for biological & bodily harms. [5] [2][12] [13] Possible biopsychosocial data collected through privacy intrusion by the dictatorial group cloud servers have also been used for financial enslavement of the

population with consumption-industrial-output calculation models and with resources & resource distribution monopolization.

Quantum cybernetics will be the future of biophysiochemistry. The origin of earth is not the origin of the universe, and the origin of human civilization is not the origin of life forms. The psychological dissection from human civilization to the perception & consciousness of the outward cosmic origins is necessary in revisiting the living space of human society. However, with the authoritarian and dictatorial information blocks enslaving people in the sciences for technological access and illicitly using technologies in the enslavement of people is creating a wide gap of consciousness divide as "the West and the rest". [12] Its adverse effects on regional & global human rights and economy have taken a toll for five years now. Its psychodynamic coercions in the cyber space both with the dualist approach to international law and with the nuclear weaponry threats in social media with semantics and server ontologies through the ICANN monopolization shown in *figure 2* is eroding the free internet with a globalization "in toto" that "matters" to the dictatorial group. [17] [26] [27][2] [28] NASA's Eyes' new keyboard monitoring function may have adjustment effects to the semantics caused crisis in the humanities.

Figure 13. Flowchart on the Dictatorial Group Supranational Force's Use of Privacy Intrusion

Albeit the hypothesis contained in *equation 5* is experimentally confirmed, the fifth cosmic force's implications for instrumentation limitations is unsolvable without substantial advancements in material science. Further implications for the quantum & physical cosmologies would be that the two disciplinary divergences will increase with gaps created by the astronomical space and electronics. Poincaré distinguished mathematical minds into logicians & analysts and intuitionists & geometers. [29] Observational cosmology is dependent on human senses, and the anterior particle states to angular momenta can only be resolved by Tycho thought experiment in quantum topologies. With regard to inverse square law, the conjecture of infinite irrationals I put forth with e^n is supposedly to be bounded between 1 and 2 if n is positive, and to 0 if n is negative.

Whereby the measurement of time external to biopsychosocial earth has been the solar centric modern astronomy milestone, the origin on the concept of time became a deductive earth-bound calculus. In the seriousness of doubt on arithmetic, the velocity of incoming light as information to the projection of matter in space is a non-objective construct but truth in the subjective nature of scientific findings. [29] Whereas Poincaré presupposes non-Euclidean to Euclidean space, I took Euclidean space as a starting point in information space by space and / or earth-based telescopes and non-Euclidean space for the destination in local universe with SR with the limitations from human trafficking. As most physicists approach the tridimensional problem in a subjective concept of time, their mathematical constructs have been mainly spatial deductive. Moving on from experiential deduction to new inductions in the natural sciences is the logical bottleneck I have been faced with and tried to overcome with my mathematical class on Coursera.

The bureaucratic order of dictatorship in the cloud & server developments have further eroded the legal system of PRC and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. Its structure of remaining and enhancing dictatorship was set since the year 1949 A.D. The dichotomy between global defense in the liberal international order and humanitarian outreaches in the satellite definitions of time may need to greater fragmentation if not properly dealt with one way or another. [28]

REFERENCES

- [1] Yang, Qiufen & Chen, Yuexin, (2001) "A Survey of the Ontology Methodology", *Application Research of Computers*, 2002, No. 4, pp. 5–7. <http://www.cqvip.com/qk/93231x/2002004/6155383.html>
- [2] Pachankis, Yang, (2022) "Epistemological Extrapolation and Individually Targetable Mass Surveillance: The Issues of Democratic Formation and Knowledge Production by Dictatorial Controls", *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, Vol. 7, Iss. 4, pp. 72–84. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6464858>
- [3] Xinhua Net, (2019) "中华人民共和国和俄罗斯联邦关于加强当代全球战略稳定的联合声明(全文)", *Xinhua News*, 06-06-2019, Report Collection on Xi, Jinping. http://www.xinhuanet.com/world/2019-06/06/c_1124588720.htm
- [4] Biddle, Tami Davis (2020) "Coercion Theory: A Basic Introduction for Practitioners", Texas: *Texas National Security Review*, Vol. 3, Iss. 2, pp. 94–109. <http://dx.doi.org/10.26153/tsw/8864>
- [5] Pachankis, Yang (2022) "Targeted Human Trafficking - The Wars between Proxy and Surrogated Economy", *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, Vol. 13, Iss. 7, pp. 398–409. https://www.ijser.org/onlineResearchPaperViewer.aspx?Targeted_Human_Trafficking_The_Wars_between_Proxy_and_Surrogated_Economy.pdf
- [6] Pachankis, Yang I. (2022) "Some Concepts of Space, Time, and Lengths in Simplified Chinese* - An Analytical Linguistics Approach", *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, Vol. 7, Iss. 6, pp. 550–562. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6796083>

- [7] Pachankis, Yang (2022) "Evidences on the PLA Interception in the Sciences for Covert Military Intelligence and Operations through Financial Operations", *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6952516>
- [8] Pachankis, Yang, (2021) "Research on the Kerr-Newman Black Hole in M82 Confirms Black Hole and White Hole Thermonuclear Binding", *Academia Letters*, Article 3199. <https://doi.org/10.20935/AL3199>
- [9] Pachankis, Yang I. (2022) "Physical Signals and their Thermonuclear Astrochemical Potentials: A Review on Outer Space Technologies", *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, Vol. 7, Iss. 5, pp. 669-674. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6618334>
- [10] Pachankis, Yang Immanuel (2022) "White Hole Observation: An Experimental Result", *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, Vol. 7, Iss. 2, pp. 779-790. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6360849>
- [11] Pachankis, Yang (2022) "Reading the Cold War through Outer Space: The Past and Future of Outer Space", *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, Vol. 13, Iss. 6, pp. 826-829. <https://doi.org/10.14299/ijser.2022.06.03>
- [12] Pachankis, Yang (2022) "The Cultural Revisionist Element behind P. R. China's Neo-Nazism: A Cross-cultural and Cross-religion Research", *International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Research and Studies*, Vol. 2, Iss. 4, pp. 435-451. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4163232>
- [13] Pachankis, Yang (2022) "MASS SURVEILLANCE, BEHAVIOURAL CONTROL, AND PSYCHOLOGICAL COERCION THE MORAL ETHICAL RISKS IN COMMERCIAL DEVICES", *CS & IT – CSCP 2022*, pp. 151-168. <https://doi.org/10.5121/csit.2022.121313>
- [14] Stirone, Shannon (2018) "Welcome to the Center of the Universe", *Longreads*. <https://longreads.com/2018/03/15/welcome-to-the-center-of-the-universe/>
- [15] Pachankis, Yang I. (2022) "White Hole Observation: An Experimental Result", *Academia*. <https://www.academia.edu/video/1wAXok>
- [16] Pachankis, Yang Immanuel (2022) "A Multi-wavelength Data Analysis with Multi-mission Space Telescopes", *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, Vol. 7, Iss. 1, pp. 701-708. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6044904>
- [17] Pachankis, Yang (2022) "The Modern Origin & Source of China's Techtransfer", *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, Vol. 13, Iss. 7, pp. 398-409. https://www.ijser.org/onlineResearchPaperViewer.aspx?Targeted_Human_Trafficking_The_Wars_between_Proxy_and_Surrogated_Economy.pdf
- [18] Bertin, E. and Arnouts, S. (1996) "SExtractor: Software for source extraction", *Astron. Astrophys., Suppl. Ser.*, Vol. 117, No. 2, pp. 393-404. <https://doi.org/10.1051/aas:1996164>
- [19] Calabretta, M. R. and Greisen, E. W. (2002) "Representations of celestial coordinates in FITS", *Astron. Astrophys.*, Vol. 395, No. 3, pp. 1077-1122. <https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20021327>
- [20] Greisen, E. W. and Calabretta, M. R. (2002) "Representations of world coordinates in FITS", *Astron. Astrophys.*, Vol. 395, No. 3, pp. 1061-1075. <https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20021326>
- [21] Greisen, E. W. and Calabretta, M. R. and Valdes, F. G. and Allen, S. L. (2006) "Representations of spectral coordinates in FITS", *Astron. Astrophys.*, Vol. 446, No. 2, pp. 747-771. <https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20053818>
- [22] Rots, Arnold H. and Bunclark, Peter S. and Calabretta, Mark R. and Allen, Steven L. and Manchester, Richard N. and Thompson, William T. (2015) "Representations of time coordinates in FITS - Time and relative dimension in space", *Astron. Astrophys.*, Vol. 574, A36. <https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201424653>
- [23] Joye, William (2019) "SAOImageDS9/SAOImageDS9 v8.0.1 (v8.0.1)", *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530958>
- [24] Krikke, Jan (2021) *Leibniz, Einstein, and China*, Olive Press.
- [25] Mushakoji, Kinhide (1997) "Multilateralism in a Multicultural World: notes for a theory of occultation", in: Cox, Robert W. (eds) *The New Realism*, pp. 84-108. United Nations University Press. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-349-25303-6_5
- [26] Wang, Hongying (1997) "Chinese Culture and Multilateralism", in: Cox, Robert W. (eds) *The New Realism*, pp. 145-161. United Nations University Press. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-349-25303-6_8
- [27] Yuan, Jing-Dong (2007) "Culture matters: Chinese approaches to arms control and disarmament", *Contemporary Security Policy*, Vol. 19, Iss. 1, 85-128. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13523269808404180>

- [28] Pachankis, Yang(2020) "Lateralism – The Globalization of US Hegemony after World War II", doctoral thesis, *Communication University of China*. https://www.ijser.org/thesis/yang_cao
- [29] Poincaré, Henri(1907) *The Value of Science*, The Science Press.

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